

INNOVATIVE ASSESSMENT PRACTICES FOR STUDENTS WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES: LEVERAGING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN INCLUSIVE CLASSROOMS.

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Abstract

In this digital era, technological innovation such as Artificial Intelligence is creating new opportunities and access for students in diverse classrooms. This technology has the potential to redefine the assessment process for students with learning disabilities, moving from the traditional method of paper and pen to innovative, and student-centered assessment practices. It has transformed the way of assessment by offering diverse digital tools and resources that are disability-friendly, enhancing feedback processes, engaging students, and providing insight into student performance. It focused on the benefits of artificial intelligence-driven assessment practices, identified some artificial intelligence tools currently available for teachers, the challenges it presents, and the prospects of the technology if appropriately used. The discourse concluded that AI has potential to increase access and quality of assessment process and practices as a pillar of prescriptive teaching-learning process for students with learning disabilities, hence the capacity of teachers and students should be improved to match the digital culture of contemporary inclusive classroom where students with learning disabilities have equal access to participate in all pedagogical activities.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Learning disabilities, Innovative assessment, and Inclusive classrooms

Introduction

Technology has brought about transformation across various domains of life, fundamentally reshaping how we interact, work, communicate, and learn. Advancements in technology have prompted changes globally, with the educational sector not left out. As one continues to integrate new tech tools into daily life, the educational sector faces persistent challenges in quality, access, participation, and assessment. Nowadays, the focus is to leverage on Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a means of improving on the efficacy and validity of assessment in inclusive pedagogy for students with learning disabilities (Gardner, O’Leary& Yuan, 2021). UNESCO (2019) suggests the need to integrate artificial intelligence in education for innovative teaching-learning process and striving for equity and access to quality education. Tomlinson (2008) asserts that innovative and inclusive assessment practices are appropriate for all students including those with learning disabilities.

Artificial intelligence in education means using a diverse set of technological tools and resources that facilitate personalized learning experiences, automate assessment processes, and enhance learning outcomes. According to Luckin, Holmes, McLaren, and Pugh (2016), AI is a technology that enables personalized and adaptive learning experiences by analysing learner data and providing tailored instruction. This innovation in educational environment and integration of artificial intelligence into assessment for inclusive teaching-learning processes have also gained global attention and relevance. The transformation is pertinent since it aligns with the philosophy and goal of fostering access, diversity, and quality as core pillars of inclusion in education and society. Al-Azawaim, Serenelli and Lundqvist (2016) argue that the application of adaptive learning technologies can significantly enhance the acquisition of skills and competencies for children with learning disabilities by personalising the educational experience.

Learners with learning disabilities have always been in classrooms, but teachers have often failed to identify them and recognise their special needs. They are frequently described as slow learners, hard to teach, daydreamers, and lazy. Learning disabilities are neurologically based processing problems. These processing problems can interfere with learning basic skills such as listening, reading, speaking, writing, spelling, and/or doing maths (Kirk 1963). They can also interfere with higher-level skills, such as organisation, time-planning, abstract-reasoning, long- or short-term memory, and attention. According to Kirk (1963), Fletcher et al, (2019), ‘learning disabilities’ is an umbrella term describing several other specific learning disabilities which include dyslexia, a specific learning disability that affects reading and related language processing skills; dyscalculia, a disability which affects a person’s understanding of numbers and the ability to learn mathematics; dysgraphia, a condition that impacts a person’s handwriting ability and fine motor skills; dyspraxia. These neurological conditions affect movement and coordination, language and speech problems, and non-verbal learning disabilities, such as the ability to process non-verbal cues, social skills, and spatial relationships. Orim (2017) observed that the nature, prevalence and implications of learning disabilities require that the teaching-learning process should be prescriptive and clinical where assessment provides data-based evidence for designing all instructional programmes, assessment of a systemic process of collecting valid information from valid sources by professionals to make decisions on education and related services for clients with disabilities. Trending transformation in the education space requires the innovative approach to

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assessment where technology such AI can be used to fill the gaps in the traditional methods (Orim &Uko 2017). This paper, therefore, provides an overview of how AI technologies can be applied as innovative assessment practices in an inclusive classroom. It focused on the benefits of artificial intelligence-driven assessment, identify some artificial intelligence tools currently available for teachers, the challenges it presents, and the prospects of the technology if appropriately used.

Benefits of using AI in Assessing Students with Learning Disabilities

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education has become increasingly prevalent, reshaping how assessments are conducted and experienced by both educators and students. Artificial Intelligence, when applied in the assessment process and practice has many benefits,including the following:

Facilitating Personalized Education Pathways:AI can tailor assessments to individual learning needs, ensuring they are tailored to their unique capabilities and abilities. According to Luckin, Holmes, Griffiths, & Forcier (2016), AI can analyze student data to deliver personalized learning experiences. They assert that adaptive learning technologies identify student strengths and weaknesses, allowing for customized assessments that enhance learning. This will allowinstructors to identify and support diverse learning pathways, since they are capable of identifying gaps in learning.This ties with the principle of differentiation of instruction (Tomlinson 2014) and promotes more effective learning.Traditional classroom settings often struggle to cater for the diverse learning needs andpace of individual students. Through adaptive learning technologies powered by AI, assessments can guide students along customized educational pathways (Popenici & Kerr, 2017). These pathways consider students' prior knowledge, interests, and goals, allowing for a more relevant and meaningful learning experience. By helping students navigate their learning trajectories, AI fosters agency and motivation, which are crucial for lifelong learning (Chen, Wang, & Razali, 2021). AI-powered platforms can adapt to each student's unique profile, offering customised learning pathways.

Continuous Feedback: AI provides instant feedback to learners, allowing them to understand their performance in real time. Shute (2008) discusses the importance of formative assessment as a tool for learning enhancement, noting that timely feedback can significantly improve students' motivation and outcomes. AI systems can monitor student progress and provide adaptive feedback, which can help in addressing gaps in understanding more effectively. According to Wai (2019), this immediacy allows for timely interventions and motivates learners to take ownership of their educational journey.

Assessment Variety: AI technologies enable diverse assessment formats, accommodating different learning preferences and abilities. According to Allen and Seaman (2014), varied assessment methods can lead to better learner engagement and retention. AI can facilitate a range of assessment types, from traditional tests to interactive simulations, allowing students to demonstrate knowledge in various ways.

Analyzing Learning Data:AI can analyze vast amounts of educational data, identifying trends and insights that inform assessment practices. According to Siemens (2013), learning

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analytics can provide valuable information on student performance and behavior, guiding educators in refining assessments to better meet the needs of diverse learners. This data-driven approach fosters a deeper understanding of student needs and promotes inclusivity within assessment frameworks (Siemens, 2013). By employing machine learning algorithms, educators can uncover patterns and trends that may not be immediately visible through conventional assessment methods (Johnson, Adams, Becker, Estrada, & Freeman, 2016).

Supporting Special Needs Education: AI applications can significantly benefit students with special needs by customizing assessments to their unique requirements. Rose & Meyer (2002) discuss Universal Design for Learning (UDL), which emphasizes inclusive learning practices. AI tools can adapt assessments, offering alternative formats and support that cater to various disabilities, thus promoting equitable access to education.

Artificial Intelligence as a Tool for Innovative Assessment Practices for Students with Learning Disabilities

Inclusive education has become the standard in the emerging society, so too is technology revolutionising learning. Some of the AI tools include:

Edcafe AI: This is an All-in-One AI-powered assessment and teaching assistant that streamlines quiz creation, personalized learning, and student progress tracking. It is used for Formative, summative, and Diagnostic assessments. This tool is best for teachers who need of a comprehensive AI tool to create, manage, and analyse assessments effortlessly while delivering personalised feedback and adaptive learning experiences. Edcafe AI has the ability to turn any material, such as a text passage, a video, or interactive content, into a quiz or an activity.

The use of Edcafe AI will turn audio into passage-based quizzes and vocabulary words to keep the interest, customized Youtube URL into quiz in minutes, with control over question types and number of questions. It also provides immediate feedback after activities and can easily track students' performances, display quiz scores and assignments, and overall progress at a glance.

Classpoint: It is an objective interactive in-class assessment and student engagement within PowerPoint. It gives interactive quizzes and gamification. It also integrates assessments into PowerPoint lessons and tracks understanding in real-time and boosts engagement. On the PowerPoint, MCQs, and short answers to fill in the blank question types are provided. The student gives life responses, and the teachers can track and adjust instruction on the fly to ensure that the students stay engaged and active. Classpoint has an award system that allows one to include point-based scoring, this boosts motivation and participation and makes lessons very engaging. It works best with formative and diagnostic assessments.

Educlick: It is an educational platform, which offers interactive learning modules, virtual classrooms and personalized study plans for students. Learning materials are adapted to the learner's needs by the use of algorithms.

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Other AI tools that can be used in an inclusive classroom for assessment include Socratic AI, Cognii AI, Gradescope, and Century Tect. The integration of AI into assessment practices presents opportunities to enhance inclusivity and personalize learning experiences. By leveraging AI technologies, educational institutions can create adaptive, unbiased, and diverse assessment approaches that cater to the individual needs of all students. This transformation not only promotes an equitable learning environment but also prepares students for a future increasingly influenced by technology.

Some AI Tools for Assessment of Students in Specific Areas of Learning Disabilities

For clarity and understanding, AI tools relevant in domains of learning disabilities are presented in the table below:

Type of Learning disabilities	AI tool	Description	Features	Application
Dyscalculia	DreamBox Learning	An adaptive math platform designed to personalize learning experiences for students struggling with math concepts.	Interactive lessons that adapt in real time to students. Use of visual models and engaging activities to build mathematical understanding.	Used to assess students' maths skills and identify areas of weakness. For example, during assessment, a student who struggles with addition may be given targeted lessons and practice problems, allowing teachers to measure progress through built-in analytics.
	NumBots:	An engaging platform that helps children improve their mathematical skills through games and challenges specifically designed to enhance number sense.	Interactive game-based learning that encourages exploration of maths concepts. Gives immediate feedback on customizable challenges.	Teachers can assign NumBots activities to reinforce maths skills for children with dyscalculia, emphasizing fundamental arithmetic in a fun and interactive way to encourage learning through play.
	Zyrobotics Math Apps:	A collection of math applications that cater to students with	Interactive game-based learning that encourages exploration of maths	In classrooms, teachers can introduce Zyrobotics apps to provide individualized math practice, helping students grasp

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		various learning difficulties, including dyscalculia.	concepts, immediate and challenges.	gives feedback and customize	fundamental concepts through engaging activities that accommodate different learning needs. E.g, a teacher can track a student's performance in a game focused on geometry to test for grasp of spatial relationships.
	modmaths	Designed for students with dyscalculia; it provides a digital platform for solving maths problems.	Students can create graphs and charts easily. Students can input maths problems directly, making it easier to manipulate equations and show their workings.		Used to evaluate students' understanding of mathematical concepts by reviewing the problems they solve within the app. The app tracks progress and highlights areas where students may struggle, providing a clear picture of their maths abilities.
Dyslexia	Read&Write by Texthelp:	It is a literacy software that provides various features to support reading and writing for students with dyslexia	Text-to-speech functionality to read text aloud. -word prediction and spell checks. Simplification tools that can modify text for easy understanding.		Can be integrated during reading assessments, enabling students to listen to the passage being read aloud while highlighting the text on the screen. E.g., during comprehension test, a student can use the text-to-speech feature to better grasp material and allow teacher to focus on verbal response rather than how well words are decoded.
	Sound literacy	An interactive literacy platform that focuses on developing phonetic awareness and phonics skills through engaging games and activities.	Phonic manipulation exercise Progress tracking. Interactive games. Personalised learning path.		Used to evaluate student's phonemic awareness development. For instance, teachers can use the platform to administer interactive phoneme segmentation tasks, where students are asked to manipulate sounds and words.
	Phonic genius	Qpp designed to help children develop phonemic awareness and phonic skills	Flash cards with words that emphasize specific phonemes. Activities include		Can be used to evaluate students' ability to recognize and manipulate phonemes.

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		through exercises.	identification, blending, and manipulation.	
	Learning Ally	An audiobook and educational platform that provides access to a vast library of recorded textbooks and literature for students with dyslexia.	Learning Ally offers human-read audiobooks paired with digital text, enabling students to follow along as they listen, which helps to improve comprehension and retention.	Instructors can use Learning Ally to supplement reading materials, allowing students with dyslexia to access complex texts aurally while developing their reading skills in an accessible format.
	Ghotit Real Writer and Reader:	A writing and reading assistance software designed for people with dyslexia and other learning disabilities.	It offers context-sensitive spell checking, grammar correction, and real-time reading assistance to help users improve their writing skills.	Teachers can implement Ghotit in writing activities, enabling students with dyslexia to compose texts more effectively and gain confidence in their writing abilities through the support of AI.
Dysgraphia	Modmath	An app designed specifically to help students with dysgraphia perform mathematical calculations without the challenges of handwriting.	ModMath allows students to complete maths problems by typing or clicking answers rather than writing by hand. It visually organizes problems and solutions, making them easier to manage.	Teachers can use ModMath as a tool during maths assessments or assignments to ensure that students with dysgraphia can demonstrate their understanding of concepts without being hindered by their handwriting difficulties.
	Notability	A note-taking application that combines handwriting, typing, and voice recordings, allowing for flexible input methods.	Students can write notes by hand (using a stylus), type, or record their voice, providing multiple ways to express their knowledge and ideas.	In a classroom setting, Notability can assist students with dysgraphia in organizing their thoughts and participating in lessons, whether it's taking notes, brainstorming, or completing assignments.

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Evernote	:Evernote is a note-taking app that allows students to capture ideas and notes through various formats, including text, audio, images, and sketches.	Its organizational features help students categorize and find information easily.	Students can use Evernotes to compile research or write reflections, allowing them to use multimedia input, thus accommodating their writing challenges.
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Source: Adapted from Schiele(2025)

Challenges of Using Artificial Intelligence for Assessment in Inclusive Classrooms

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in educational assessment practices has garnered significant interest, particularly as educators seek to personalize learning experiences for diverse student populations. However, while AI holds promise for enhancing assessment methods in inclusive classrooms, it also presents various challenges that must be critically examined. The effective implementation of AI in educational settings raises issues regarding data privacy, algorithmic bias, the reliability and validity of assessments, the potential depersonalization of learning, teacher readiness, and resistance to change. Addressing these challenges is crucial to ensuring that AI serves as an equitable tool for all students.

Data Privacy and Security: One of the primary concerns associated with AI in assessment is the protection of student data. AI systems often require large datasets to function effectively, raising significant issues related to data privacy, consent, and security. In inclusive classrooms, the stakes are particularly high, as student data may contain sensitive information about disabilities, learning difficulties, and personal backgrounds. This raises ethical dilemmas regarding how data is collected, stored, and utilized (Jones, 2019). If proper measures are not in place, breaches of data privacy could undermine trust among students, parents, and educators.

Algorithmic Bias and Fairness: Another significant challenge is the issue of algorithmic bias, which can perpetuate existing inequalities in educational assessments. AI algorithms trained on historical data may reflect systemic biases that disproportionately affect marginalized groups, including students from underrepresented backgrounds or those with diverse learning needs. Geiger and Halfaker (2016) highlight how biases in training data can lead to unfair evaluations, potentially disadvantaging specific groups of students and exacerbating educational inequities.

Reliability and Validity of AI Assessments: The reliability and validity of AI assessments are essential considerations in any educational setting. The effectiveness of AI tools hinges on their ability to measure student knowledge and skills accurately. Concerns arise about whether AI-generated assessments can provide valid results that reflect diverse learners’ capabilities, particularly those with unique educational needs (Baker & Inventado, 2014).

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Depersonalization of Learning: While AI has the potential to offer personalized feedback and adaptive assessments, there is a considerable risk of depersonalizing the learning experience in inclusive classrooms. The human connection and relational aspect of education are essential, particularly for students who may require additional emotional and social support (Luckin, 2016). The effective integration of AI assessment tools also requires that educators are adequately trained to utilize these technologies. Many teachers may lack the necessary skills or confidence to implement AI in their assessment practices effectively, limiting the potential benefits of these innovations (Ahn & Lim, 2019). Insufficient professional development opportunities can lead to suboptimal use of AI tools, which may not fully address the diverse needs of learners.

Resistance to Change: Finally, resistance to change can impede the adoption of AI technologies in assessment practices. Educators, students, and parents may be skeptical about the efficacy of AI assessments or concerned about the implications of using technology in place of traditional teaching methods. Zhao (2019) discusses the cultural resistance to adopting AI technologies in education, emphasizing the need for stakeholder engagement to foster an atmosphere of innovation. To overcome this resistance, clear communication about AI's benefits and active involvement of educators and parents in the process is essential.

Ethical Considerations in the Use of Artificial Intelligence

The use of AI in assessing children with learning disabilities raises several ethical concerns, especially within the diverse cultural context. Some examples of the key ethical concerns are:

Bias and fairness: AI systems can inevitably perpetuate bias present in training data, leading to inaccurate assessments for children from diverse backgrounds. According to Beede et al (2019), it is important to make sure that AI tools are developed with representative data to avoid inequitable outcomes. For example, in some countries where more than 250 languages are spoken, an AI assessment tool primarily trained on data from dominant languages may misinterpret or misrepresent the abilities of children who speak minority languages. This could lead to unfair assessments, mislabeling students without the proper identification of their skills and needs.

Privacy and data security: AI assessment tools collect sensitive educational and personal data. Sharma et al. (2020) suggest that the safeguarding and confidentiality of student data is very important. AI assessment tools should have transparent data management practices to secure and safeguard the sensitive data of students, particularly given the limited awareness about data privacy laws in many communities.

Informed consent: In many countries, there are cultural norms and levels of education concerning technology, which can affect students and their parents' understanding of AI systems. Before a student is assessed, using AI, the parents must give permission, and the child must accept to be so assessed. Taddeo and Floridi (2018) argue that obtaining informed consent is essential but may be challenging in contexts where families might not fully understand the implications of AI-driven assessments. In many communities, there might be little familiarity with AI technologies, so parents and guardians may hesitate in giving informed consent because they may not fully comprehend how AI assessment works. Ensuring that consent processes are transparent and culturally appropriate is necessary.

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Equity of access: The implementation of AI in educational assessment can create disparities in access to resources and support. There is the risk that the adoption of AI in educational assessment disproportionately benefits urban versus rural schools in some countries. Schools in Urban areas may gain access to advanced technology, while those in rural regions may lack adequate resources. Heffernan and Heffernan (2014) indicate that such disparities can widen the educational gap, leaving students in rural areas without the necessary support for learning disabilities. An example can be seen when a school in Yaounde, the capital city of Cameroon, implements an AI-driven assessment tool while in a rural school in the North West region struggles with basic educational materials. This disparity can create unequal opportunities for children with learning disabilities across the country.

Over-reliance on technology: The increasing reliance on AI tools for assessments may overlook the human judgment of the needs of a student. The part played by teachers and other professionals in identifying and remedying learning needs maybe overshadowed. Luckin et al. (2016) noted that effective assessments should integrate human insights alongside AI assessments. In this light, teachers should remain involved in the assessment process in order to understand the student's learning environment that affects learning.

Conclusion

The integration of artificial intelligence into assessment practices provides an opportunity for equity, equality and fairness in the assessment of student with learning disabilities. In inclusive classrooms marked by diverse learning needs and abilities, AI platforms such as Edcafe, Socratic, Cognii, Google Class, Classpoint Grade Tech and Century Tech, can personalise assessments based on unique needs and provide timely feedback for adjusting instruction if needed. However, the use of these technologies should be guided by policies and legislation, and ethical considerations should be paid to the challenges that may arise, like data privacy, Algorithmic Bias, and Fairness. While AI represents a powerful tool for enhancing assessment in inclusive classrooms, several challenges must be addressed to maximize its potential. These challenges include data privacy and security concerns, algorithmic bias, the reliability, and validity of assessments, the potential for depersonalization of learning experiences, teacher training and readiness, and resistance to change. By acknowledging and proactively addressing these challenges, educational stakeholders can work toward implementing AI in ways that support inclusive educational practices, which will ultimately foster equitable opportunities for all learners. Based on this discourse, the following suggestions are made:

- The philosophy of UDL and inclusivity should be applied in the design and development of AI tools for the teaching-learning process.
- There should be collaboration between teachers, learners, policy makers, and other stakeholders building digital capacity required for effective use of AI tools.
- There should be awareness on ethical education on AI technology as respect for human elements in the education industry
- Policy and legislative framework on AI should guide the application across all sectors of the economy.

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